

1 Trisaccharides isomers, galactinol and osmotic imbalance associated with CO₂ stress in
2 strawberries.

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23 ABSTRACT

24 Treatment with high CO₂ atmospheres is effective in preventing strawberry decay and
25 increasing firmness. Nevertheless, CO₂ stress generates energy disturbances associated
26 with a high rate of fermentation. This study was designed to measure the impact of high
27 CO₂ stress (3 d, 40 kPa CO₂) and its subsequent removal on fruit quality, osmotic
28 balance and water relations. Fructo-trisaccharides isomers and raffinose were
29 characterized and quantified by mass spectrometry (MS and MS²). CO₂ stress removal
30 was marked by both a rapid upsurge in the ratio of unfreezable water to total water and
31 an osmotic adjustment prompted by the accumulation of soluble sugars, 1-kestose,
32 raffinose and galactinol. Due to strong increase in galactinol concentrations, we propose
33 it as a suitable biomarker for fruit having undergone stresses associated with osmotic
34 imbalance.

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36 *Keywords:* galactinol, raffinose, fructans, CO₂ stress, firmness, strawberries.

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48 **1. Introduction**

49 Strawberries are classified as a high CO₂ tolerant fruit. High CO₂ atmospheres have
50 been used successfully to control fungal decay and to maintain or even increase
51 firmness during storage at low temperature, without producing an adverse effect on fruit
52 quality (Smith and Skog, 1992; Larsen and Watkins, 1995; Harker et al., 2000).
53 However, when the CO₂ levels exceed the tolerance threshold, a series of alterations are
54 induced such as: the flesh becoming visually blue-red and water-soaked (Ke et al.,
55 1991), a metabolically harmful accumulation of fermentative metabolites (Ke et al.,
56 1994) and a marked reduction in both ATP and adenylate energy charge (Blanch et al.,
57 2015a). When sustained fermentation is maintained and ATP levels became too low to
58 sustain the energy requirements for cell repair, oxidative damage provokes an increase
59 in lipid peroxidation that is reflected in high levels of malondialdehyde (Blanch et al.,
60 2015a) and a loss of membrane integrity. Our working hypothesis is that given the
61 metabolic energy disturbances sustained by the high ethanolic fermentation that occurs
62 at excessively high CO₂ concentrations, changes in the carbohydrate reserve that acts as
63 an energy source would also be witnessed. Aerobic fermentation can also be induced by
64 other stresses, which is considered an important switch regulating carbohydrate
65 metabolism (Tadege et al., 1999).

66 Apart from their involvement in energy reserve mobilization, fructo-oligosaccharides
67 (FOS) and raffinose-oligosaccharides (RFOs) are associated with protection during
68 different kinds of plant stress (Hisano et al., 2008; Van den Ende and Valluru, 2009;
69 Rohloff et al., 2012). However, there are significant gaps in our understanding of the
70 protective role of FOSs, in part due to their heterogeneous nature. FOS represent
71 complex mixtures of isomers (differing in the bonds between the monomeric sugar
72 units) and oligomers (differing in chain length). As such, it is essential to employ

73 methods suitable for the separation, analysis and unambiguous characterization of FOS
74 isomers.

75 In the case of trisaccharides, different isomers constitute the templates for further
76 elongation that give rise to inulins, levans and neo-series fructans, such as 1-kestose, 6-
77 kestose and 6G-kestose, respectively. ~~The synthesis of 1-kestose from sucrose is~~
78 ~~catalyzed by the sucrose:sucrose 1-fructosyltransferase enzyme (1-SST), while~~
79 ~~sucrose:fructan 6-fructosyltransferase (6-SFT) produces 6-kestose from sucrose~~
80 ~~(Livingston et al., 2009). The synthesis of neo-kestose (6G-kestose) requires~~
81 ~~fructan:fructan 6G-fructosyltransferase (6G-FFT) and it uses 1-kestose as a fructose~~
82 ~~donor, transferring the fructose to the glucose residue of sucrose through a $\beta(2\text{-}6)$~~
83 ~~linkage (Vijn and Smeekens, 1999).~~ They are all isomers with an identical chemical
84 formula, which in turn means that they produce the same molecular ions. Since each
85 isomer is an extension of sucrose, the differential partitioning of sucrose into each
86 isomer acquires special relevance in growing programs that target greater sucrose
87 content in strawberries.

88 ~~Mass spectrometry (MS) is an important tool for the structural analysis of carbohydrates~~
89 ~~as it is a very sensitive, precise and versatile technique. Using MS, isomeric~~
90 ~~oligosaccharides can be separated and specific oligomers identified based on their~~
91 ~~retention time and the mass to charge (m/z) ratio.~~ The use of mass spectrometry (MSⁿ)
92 to analyze the fragmentation patterns of molecular ions has become a key tool for the
93 structural analysis and characterization of oligosaccharides. The three DP3 fructan
94 isomers can be distinguished by their MS fragmentation patterns without the need for
95 authentic standards (Verspreet et al., 2014). As such, we have employed MS and MS² to
96 identify and analyze the accumulation of trisaccharide FOS isomers in strawberries.

97 As with FOS, an increase in RFOs is often associated with environmental stress,
98 especially that induced by water deficit and temperature stress (Taji et al., 2002;
99 Sengupta et al., 2015). The biosynthesis of the raffinose trisaccharide, the smallest RFO,
100 begins with the formation of galactinol from uridine diphosphate galactose (UDP-
101 galactose) and *myo*-inositol. Galactinol, a galactosyl-donor exclusive to the raffinose
102 biosynthetic pathway, plays an important regulatory role in carbon-partitioning between
103 sucrose and RFOs. In raffinose synthesis, uridine diphosphate glucose (UDP-glucose)
104 must be used to produce RFO rather than for glucose and fructose production in order to
105 sustain glycolysis (Nishizawa et al., 2008). Indeed, the levels of galactinol and raffinose
106 increase dramatically during cold acclimatization in the leaves of the woodland
107 strawberry (Rohloff et al., 2012), although only galactinol is clearly associated with
108 cold tolerance (Davik et al., 2013).

109 Trisaccharides and simple sugars can protect cells osmotically and stabilize biological
110 structures (Hare et al., 1998). They also alter the physicochemical properties of aqueous
111 solutions (Miller and Pablo, 2000; Furuki, 2002; Blanch et al., 2012), suggesting that
112 carbohydrate-water interactions represent a significant part of their protective functions.
113 Thus, this study was designed to measure the impact of both high CO₂ stress and its
114 subsequent removal on organic osmolytes, including sucrose-derived trisaccharides, and
115 how this relates to the cellular water status and osmotic balance. ~~Trisaccharides were~~
116 ~~analyzed by MS, evaluating tri-FOS isomers, raffinose and the related UDP-glucose,~~
117 ~~UDP-galactose and galactinol. The effect of high CO₂ stress was assessed on the water~~
118 ~~relations and the quality parameters of the fruit, including firmness, pH, titratable~~
119 ~~acidity, external color, unfreezable to total water ratio, water potential and solute~~
120 ~~concentration. The protective capacity of compounds from the FOS and RFO families is~~
121 ~~discussed.~~ For that, the levels of UDP-sugars as well as the total possible trisaccharides

122 of both RFO and FOS family involved in sucrose metabolism have been quantified in
123 strawberries at the end of treatment and after transfer to atmospheric CO₂ for one day.
124 Also assessment of water relations and quality traits related to textural properties and
125 color was assessed. Our data point out to a specific increase in solutes and sucrose
126 related trisaccharides in fruit emerging from high CO₂ stress, associated with water
127 status recovery. Also notable is the firmness enhancement in 40 kPa CO₂ fruit that was
128 not reversed after transfer to atmospheric CO₂.

129

130 **2. Materials and Methods**

131 *2.1. Plant material*

132 The strawberries used in this study (*Fragaria vesca* Mara des Bois) were grown in an
133 orchard in San Sebastian de los Reyes (Madrid, Spain) according to the Regulatory
134 Committee on Organic Production guidelines. Ripe strawberries of uniform size were
135 harvested in the early morning and transported to the Institute of Food Science,
136 Technology and Nutrition within 2 h. Ripe fruit (10.4 %) of total soluble solids free of
137 defects ~~was~~ ~~were~~ placed in plastic boxes (0.5 kg of fruit per box, approximately 45 per
138 box) and 15 plastic boxes of strawberries were each placed in each 1 m³ treatment
139 container at 0 °C (±0.5) and 95% RH. The strawberries were maintained for three days
140 in atmospheric CO₂ or in presence of 40 kPa CO₂, at a constant O₂ concentration of 20
141 kPa and with a constant flow rate of 100 mL/min. At the end of the 40 kPa CO₂
142 treatment, ~~the fruit was~~ ~~strawberries were~~ transferred to atmospheric CO₂ for one further
143 day ~~keeping at the same temperature~~ (0 °C). The gas composition was measured twice
144 daily using a Check Mate 9900 O₂, O₂/CO₂ headspace analyzer (Dansensor España,
145 S.L.U.). The quality attributes of 45 strawberries from each of the lots was assessed
146 (total soluble solids, pH, titratable acidity and external color), and the texture of another

147 15 strawberries was analyzed (three replicates of 5 fruit). A further 45 strawberries were
148 removed at random and divided into three batches of 15 berries, frozen in liquid
149 nitrogen and stored at $-80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for additional analyses. Thus, each biological replicate
150 analyzed here was composed of 15 pooled strawberries.

151

152 *2.2. Determination of fruit quality*

153 Firmness was assessed in three replicates from each lot by measuring the maximum
154 shear force using a Kramer shear cell of a TA.HD Plus Stable Microsystems Analyser
155 (Stable Microsystems Ltd; Surrey, England). For each assay, five intact strawberries of
156 similar size (adding up 50 g) were horizontally placed in the Kramer shear cell. The
157 crosshead speed was 5 mm/sec and the firmness values were expressed in Newtons.

158 The soluble solids content was determined in the juice obtained from the fresh pulp of
159 strawberries using a digital refractometer (Atago PR-101, Atago, Japan). The titratable
160 acidity was analyzed in homogenized fruit tissues by titration with 0.1 N NaOH to pH
161 8.1 (Mettler DL-70, Mettler-Toledo, Spain) and the results were expressed in relation to
162 the percentage of malic acid. Triplicate measurements were taken, at least.

163 External color was measured on three sides of 15 strawberries using a Konica Minolta
164 CM-3500d colorimeter and following the CIE (Commission International de
165 l'Eclairage) system. L^* , a^* , b^* and C values were measured to describe a three-
166 dimensional color space, and they were used to calculate the chroma $(C) = (a^2 + b^2)^{1/2}$.
167 L^* indicates lightness from 0 (completely opaque or black) to 100 (completely
168 transparent or white), a positive a^* indicates redness ($-a^*$ is greenness) and a positive b^*
169 value yellowness ($-b^*$ is blueness).

170

171 *2.3. Water status*

172 Strawberry water status was assessed by measuring fruit water potential, total water
173 content, unfreezable and freezable water content, and the ratio of unfreezable to total
174 water.

175 Fruit water potential was measured using a Dewpoint Potential Meter, WP4 (Decagon
176 Devices, Inc., USA) according to the method of Blanch et al. (2012).

177 Calorimetric determinations were made using a DSC822eMettler-Toledo differential
178 scanning calorimeter (Mettler-Toledo Inc., Columbus, OH, USA) equipped with a
179 liquid nitrogen cooling accessory and following the method of Goñi et al. (2007). The
180 resulting thermograms were evaluated and the heating scan was used to determine the
181 $T_{f(\text{onset})}$, corresponding to the equilibrium freezing temperature and the melting enthalpy.
182 The melting enthalpy of the samples and that of deionized water, together with the total
183 water (T_W), allowed the freezable (F_W) and unfreezable water (U_W) content to be
184 determined. For differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), at least five measurements
185 were made on each sampling day and the U_W was calculated as:

$$186 \quad U_W = T_W - F_W$$

187 where

$$188 \quad F_W = \Delta H_{\text{sample}} / \Delta H_{\text{pure water}}$$

189 Both F_W and U_W were expressed relative to the dry mass and the T_W was determined
190 after the stable weight had been obtained by oven-drying at 65 °C. The ratio of the U_W
191 to T_W was calculated and expressed as a percentage.

192

193 *2.4. Extraction and analysis of FOS and RFO trisaccharides by MS and MS²*

194 Frozen berry samples (approximately 3 g) were homogenized in 4 mL of ultra-pure
195 water and the mixture was boiled under reflux in a water bath for 15 min. After cooling,
196 the samples were sonicated for 10 min at 40 °C and the pH of each sample was adjusted

197 to 7.5 with 10% NH₄OH. The samples were then centrifuged for 15 min at 14,700 g and
198 the supernatants were filtered through a 0.45 μm pore size membrane.

199 A preliminary identification of the compounds to be studied was made by quadrupole
200 time-of-flight (QTOF) mass spectrometry. These analyses were performed on an
201 Agilent 1200 series Liquid Chromatography system, with a quaternary pump G1311A
202 and an integrated degasser G1322A, a thermostated autosampler G1367B and a
203 thermostated column compartment G1316A. This apparatus was coupled to an Agilent
204 6530 accurate-mass QTOF LC-MS apparatus with ESI-Jet Stream Technology (Agilent
205 Technologies, Waldbronn, Germany). A 5 μL sample was separated at 30 °C on a
206 Thermo Hypercarb column (100 mm x 2.1 mm, 5 μm particle size: Thermo Fisher
207 Scientific, Bremen, Germany), and eluted using a mobile phase made up of a mixture of
208 5 mM ammonium formate (solvent A) and acetonitrile (solvent B) that was applied at a
209 flow rate of 0.4 mL min⁻¹. The solvent gradient changed as follows: 0–1 min, 5% B; 1–5
210 min, 5–10% B; 5–10 min, 10% B; 10–20 min, 10–50% B; 20–25 min, 50% B; 25–30
211 min, 50–0% B; 30–35 min, 0% B.

212 Q-TOF acquisition was achieved at high resolution (2 GHz) in MS¹ acquisition mode
213 (Min Range m/z 100; Max Range m/z 2500). Ionization was achieved by atmospheric
214 pressure electrospray ionization (ESI) with a drying gas flow rate of 12 L min⁻¹ at 350
215 °C, a sheath gas flow of 6.5 L min⁻¹ at 300 °C, a nebulizer at 45 psi, and a cap voltage of
216 4000 V, nozzle voltage of 0 V, fragmentor voltage of 200 V and skimmer voltage of 65
217 V.

218 The experiments were carried out at negative polarity with reference masses (m/z) of
219 119.0363 and 966.0007 to maximize sensitivity. A constant collision energy of 30 eV
220 was employed for auto MS² experiments, using the Data Acquisition (version B.04.01)
221 and Qualitative Analysis (version B.04.00) of the MassHunter Workstation software

222 (Agilent Technologies). Samples (5 μL) were injected to analyze the compounds
223 quantified in negative polarity. The three peaks in the m/z 503 selected ion
224 chromatogram for oligosaccharide trimers correspond to 1-kestose [O - β -D-
225 glucopyranosyl-(1-2)- O - β -D-fructofuranosyl-(1-2)-D-fructofuranoside], 6G-kestose
226 (also called neokestose) [O - β -D-glucopyranosyl-(2-6)- O - β -D-fructofuranosyl-(1-2)-D-
227 fructofuranoside] and raffinose [β -D-fructofuranosyl α -D-galactopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 6)- α -D-
228 glucopyranoside]. An authentic standard of 1-kestose eluted at 7.2 min and exhibited a
229 different MS^2 spectrum to the other isomers. To identify 6G-kestose we analyzed
230 lyophilized onion extracts that are reported to accumulate only two fructan trimers: 1-
231 kestose and 6G-kestose (Shiomi et al., 1997; Benkeblia et al., 2005). The third peak
232 identified as raffinose was confirmed with an authentic standard.

233 These trisaccharides were quantified from the areas of their chromatographic peaks
234 obtained in extracted ion chromatogram (EIC) mode by comparison with a calibration
235 curve obtained with 1-kestose and raffinose external standards purchased from Sigma
236 (Steinheim, Germany). These standards are specific for HPLC assays and their purity
237 was $\geq 95\%$. The compounds analyzed were expressed as mg kg^{-1} fresh weight and the
238 data represent the means of the three biological replicates, with two different technical
239 measurements for each.

240

241 *2.5. Extraction and analysis of UDP-sugars and galactinol by MS and MS^2*

242 UDP-sugars (UDP-glucose and UDP-galactose) and galactinol were extracted by the
243 same procedure and a preliminary identification of the compounds was made by QTOF
244 MS as described above. A 2 μL sample was separated on a Tracer Excel C8 120 ODS-B
245 column (25cm x 0.46 cm, 5 μm particle size: Teknokroma, Spain), and eluted with a
246 mobile phase made up of 0.1% formic acid (solvent A) and 0.1% formic acid in

247 acetonitrile (solvent B) at a flow rate of 0.4 mL min⁻¹. The solvent gradient changed as
248 follows: 0–5 min 0% B; 5–22 min 0–50% B; 22–25 min 50% B; 25–28 min 50–0% B; 249
28–35 min 0% B.

250 The same QTOF acquisition method was used for these compounds as that described
251 above, injecting 2 µL samples to quantify the compounds in negative polarity. The peak
252 with m/z 341, and two more peaks with m/z 565 were selected in the ion chromatogram
253 that correspond to galactinol, UDP-glucose and UDP-galactose, respectively. Galactinol
254 and UDP-glucose were identified with authentic standards, while UDP-galactose was
255 identified by its exact mass and by its similitude to UDP-glucose in terms of the
256 fragmentation pattern. These compounds were quantified from the areas of their
257 chromatographic peaks in EIC mode by comparison with the calibration curves obtained
258 with the galactinol and UDP-glucose external standards purchased from Sigma
259 (Steinheim, Germany). These standards are specific for HPLC assays and their purity
260 was ≥95%. The compounds analyzed were expressed in µg kg⁻¹ fresh weight and the
261 data represent the means of the three biological replicates with two different technical
262 measurements for each.

263

264 *2.6. Statistical analysis*

265 The results were presented as the mean ± standard deviation (SD) and the statistical
266 analysis was carried out with SPSS Software version 19.0. One-way analysis of
267 variance (ANOVA) was performed and a multiple comparison of the means were
268 performed with the Tukey's test at a significance level of 0.05. The Pearson's test was
269 used to find the correlation between soluble solids and the freezing onset temperature.

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272 3. Results and Discussion

273 3.1. Fruit quality and water relations parameters

274 The chromatic characteristics of the strawberry's skin were assessed at harvest, after 3 d
275 of storage at 0 °C in air with atmospheric CO₂ or with 40 kPa CO₂ (CO₂ stress), and
276 after subsequent transfer to air (CO₂ stress removal) (Table 1). The treatment with 40
277 kPa CO₂ increased the lightness of the skin (reflected by an increase in L*) and lowered
278 the C* values relative to those of strawberries at harvest. The decrease in C* and the
279 increase in L* were also observed in fruit maintained in atmospheric CO₂, although the
280 most significant changes in the external color of strawberries were observed after CO₂
281 stress removal, when the external color became lighter (the highest L* values) and less
282 intensely rose red (the lowest values of a* and C*). The pH and the titratable acidity
283 data indicated a slight (0.1 pH unit) but significant increase in pH, paralleled by a
284 corresponding decrease in titratable acidity in 40 kPa CO₂ fruit, that was not reversed
285 after transfer to atmospheric CO₂ (Table 1). The more marked changes in lightness, pH
286 and titratable acidity observed after storage in 40 kPa CO₂ are in line with those
287 reported elsewhere, even when considering lower CO₂ concentrations (Holcroft and
288 Kader, 1999).

289 In terms of the evolution of firmness measured through the Kramer's shear test, after 3
290 d of storage at 0 °C strawberries treated with 40 kPa CO₂ levels were firmer than fruit
291 after harvest or those stored at ambient CO₂. High CO₂ treatment (20 kPa) at low
292 temperature was previously shown to enhance the firmness of several strawberry
293 cultivars (Smith and Skog, 1992; Larsen and Watkins, 1995). Our data indicate that this
294 increase in firmness was not-reversible after transfer to atmospheric CO₂, in line with
295 that reported by Harker et al., (2000). Fruit firmness is determined by several factors,
296 including structural features of the tissue, the volume and composition of the

297 intercellular spaces, chemical composition and physical properties of cell walls and the
298 cell water potential (Harker et al., 2000; Gómez Galindo et al., 2004). Our data indicate
299 that there were small differences in the water potential of CO₂-stressed fruit with respect
300 to fruit at harvest (Table 1). In the absence of differences in water potential, higher
301 firmness of CO₂-treated strawberries can be the result of the effect of ethanol on cell
302 wall structural carbohydrates. High ethanol levels have been reported by us only in
303 CO₂-treated fruit either at the end of treatment or after transfer to air for one day
304 (Blanch et al., 2015), as well as ethanol treatment impact on the chemical properties and
305 the content of cell wall proteins (Herppich et al., 2015).

306 When the total soluble solids were assessed, there was a significant decrease in the total
307 soluble solids content of CO₂ stressed strawberries relative to those at harvest (Fig. 1A).
308 By contrast, a significant increase in total soluble solids was evident one day after
309 transfer to atmospheric CO₂, reaching values significantly higher than those in fruit at
310 harvest. As expected, this increase in soluble solids was strongly correlated with a
311 decrease in the freezing onset temperature ($T_{f \text{ (onset)}}$) determined calorimetrically ($R = -$
312 0.95 , $P = 0.05$). While similar $T_{f \text{ (onset)}}$ values were found in fruit at harvest and in
313 untreated fruit, a sharp increase in the $T_{f \text{ (onset)}}$ paralleled the decrease in soluble solids in
314 CO₂ stressed strawberries, reaching values of -1.9 °C (Fig. 1B). Conversely, a decrease
315 of almost 1.5 °C was observed after the release from CO₂ stress, indicative of an
316 accumulation of solutes. Such solute accumulation paralleled the increase in the U_w/T_w
317 ratio (Fig. 1C), explained by an increase in the amount of U_w . The U_w/T_w ratio
318 decreased 2.4-fold in CO₂ stressed strawberries relative to those at harvest. The U_w/T_w
319 ratio in fruit maintained at atmospheric CO₂ was mainly explained by a significant loss
320 in the total water content. Our results suggest that the acute fermentative metabolism
321 caused by high CO₂ stress significantly decreased the levels of fermentable sugars,

322 causing osmotic depression and a loss of unfreezable water, which was reversed when
323 CO₂-stressed fruit were transferred to ambient CO₂. After CO₂ removal the small
324 changes in water potential (Table 1) together with the accumulation of solutes (Fig. 1A,
325 1B) may provoke the entry of water into strawberry cells, increasing their turgidity.
326 Indeed, the loss of extracellular water has been visualized by low temperature scanning
327 electron microscopy (Blanch et al., 2015b).

328

329 *3.2. Identification of sucrose-related trisaccharides: 1-Kestose and 6G-kestose (tri-* 330 *FOS) and raffinose (tri-RFO_s)*

331 The tri-saccharides (DP3) in the samples that were closely related to sucrose were
332 identified and analyzed. The peak data obtained in the QTOF analysis indicated the
333 exact mass molecular ion, the tentative molecular formula, the score (percent), the main
334 fragments observed in MS², and the tentative FOS and RFO trisaccharides present (as
335 summarized in Table 2). 1-Kestose, 6G-kestose isomers and raffinose were identified
336 through the exact mass and fragmentation characteristics obtained when the MS was
337 performed in negative mode to heighten the sensitivity and hence, lower the detection
338 limits. The peaks in the extracted ion chromatogram (EIC) from the HPLC-ESI-QTOF
339 analysis were characterized by examining the mass spectra at the peak retention time.
340 No 6-kestose was detected in Mara des Bois strawberries. 1-Kestose, 6G-kestose and
341 raffinose trisaccharides were all well-resolved on the Hypercarb column, each with a
342 clearly different and reproducible MS² spectrum (Fig. 2). The elution profile of these
343 compounds from the fruit was 1-kestose first, with a retention time of 7.20 min,
344 followed by 6G-kestose with a retention time of 8.65 min and raffinose with a retention
345 time of 9.30 min. The 6G-kestose obtained had a strong homology to onion fructan.

346 There were two major ion products in the fragmentation of 1-kestose from the fruit, m/z
347 323 and m/z 179 (Fig. 3A). The first fragment ion contains two fructose units, while the
348 second major fragment, with a m/z of 179, was assigned as anhydrofructose (Fang and
349 Bendiak, 2007), representing a non-reducing monosaccharide containing the original
350 glycosidic oxygen (Fig. 3A). This fragmentation pattern was very similar to that of the
351 1-kestose standard and the 1-kestose isomer from lyophilized onion. The analysis of the
352 6G-kestose fragmentation pattern (Fig. 3B) obtained in negative mode also showed one
353 major ion product with a m/z of 179. In the lower mass range, the ion at m/z 221 could
354 be assigned as fructosyl-glycolaldehyde (Harrison et al., 2012). This ion product did not
355 appear in the 1-kestose fragmentation pattern. Only one major ion product was evident
356 in the fragmentation profile of raffinose, m/z 221, a pattern that differed from that of 1-
357 kestose and 6G-kestose in fruit (Fig. 3C).

358 This is the first time that all these isomers have been characterized and quantified by
359 HPLC-ESI-QTOF. Examination of the MS^2 spectra of the three peaks with a m/z of 503
360 shows both clear differences, as well as similarities in the spectra, along with the
361 fragmentation observed. We suggest that the differences between 1-kestose and 6G-
362 kestose fragmentation are associated with the different types of bonding in the fructan
363 series. 1-Kestose is comprised of two fructose units and one terminal glucose unit but
364 with no final reducing group. 6G-Kestose, contains a glucose moiety between two
365 fructofuransosyl units that are extended by β 2-1 linkages. As expected, there was a
366 clear relationship between the structure and the MS^2 spectra of 1-kestose, 6G-kestose
367 and raffinose.

368

369 *3.3. Effect of high CO_2 stress and reversibility on the content of tri-FOS isomers,*
370 *raffinose and galactinol.*

371 When compared to fruit at harvest, the levels of 1-kestose decreased in 40 kPa CO₂
372 stressed strawberries, reaching values of 28.6 mg kg⁻¹ fresh weight, although
373 interestingly this trend was reversed after CO₂ removal (Fig. 4A). By contrast, the 6G-
374 kestose content remained stable and no further increase was observed ~~in this tri-FOS~~
375 ~~isomer~~ (Fig. 4B). Since, only 1-kestose increased after transfer to air, this isomer could
376 fulfil a specialized function. There was a stronger decrease in 1-kestose and 6G-kestose
377 in the untreated fruit stored in ambient CO₂.

378 The concentration of raffinose, an α -galactosyl extension of sucrose, was 26 mg kg⁻¹
379 fresh weight in untreated strawberries stored in ambient CO₂ at 0 °C (atmospheric CO₂),
380 a value similar to that of tri-FOS (Fig. 4C). When compared with fruit at harvest, there
381 was less raffinose in 40 kPa CO₂ strawberries but there was more in those stored at
382 atmospheric CO₂. After relief from the CO₂ stress, the amount of raffinose returned to
383 levels comparable with those at harvest. The evolution of raffinose followed a similar
384 pattern to that of 1-kestose.

385 Several protective functions have been attributed to simple sugars, FOS and RFOs, and
386 their accumulation is generally associated with tolerance to distinct environmental
387 stresses (Mahajan and Tuteja, 2005). Thus, the significant decrease in tri-FOS and
388 raffinose in untreated fruit stored in ambient CO₂ at 0 °C can indicate a loss of
389 protection, and consequently, a greater susceptibility to injury at this temperature.
390 Specifically, fructans provide protection from the damage caused to proteins and
391 membranes by severe low temperature. Increased levels of raffinose and galactinol have
392 been reported during cold acclimation (Nishizawa et al. 2008; Korn et al. 2010). In
393 peach fruit, galactinol and raffinose are the metabolites that show the greatest increase
394 in response to either short heat treatment or cold storage (Lauxmann et al., 2014),
395 suggesting that these compounds may be crucial for the heat treatment-induced

396 protection against chilling injury. Our data indicate that the enhanced accumulation of
397 these water-soluble trisaccharides after high CO₂ removal paralleled the increase in the
398 unfreezable water fraction. Thus, we suggest that their protective function depends on
399 their ability to retain water. A comparative thermal study of aqueous solutions of
400 different sugars (Blanch et al., 2012) indicate that the capacity of raffinose and 1-
401 kestose to interfere with water molecules were three time more than that of
402 monosaccharides. From this perspective, the modification of sucrose metabolism
403 towards the accumulation of 1-kestose and raffinose might contribute to the recovery of
404 water status after CO₂ stress removal.

405 Galactinol, α -D-Gal-(1→1)-L-*myo*-inositol, is present at low concentrations in Mara des
406 Bois strawberries (40 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ fresh weight) at harvest and it increased to 92 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$
407 fresh weight when strawberries emerged from high CO₂ stress (Fig. 4D). Several roles
408 have been attributed to galactinol (ElSayed et al., 2014; Sengupta et al., 2015) and it has
409 been reported that galactinol concentrations drop clearly during water deficit stress,
410 except for a transient peak at 70% relative water content (Peters et al., 2007). In leaves,
411 the most cold-tolerant strawberry genotypes exhibit the lowest levels of galactinol after
412 acclimation (Davik et al., 2013), suggesting the potential of galactinol as a cold
413 tolerance biomarker in leaves. Since galactinol increased in conjunction with raffinose,
414 this biosynthetic pathway would appear to be strongly activated in fruit recovering from
415 exposure to excessively high CO₂. Hence, we suggest that galactinol could be an early
416 indicator of the energy metabolism activated in fruit emerging from osmotic depression
417 and cellular water stress caused by high CO₂ stress. Other possible protective functions
418 associated with its capacity to retain water molecules will require further study.

419

420 3.4. Effect of high CO₂ stress and reversibility on UDP-galactose and UDP-glucose
421 content, and the hexose/sucrose ratio in strawberries

422 ~~As with the concentrations of galactinol, the UDP-galactose required for RFO~~
423 ~~biosynthesis also increased after CO₂ stress removal, although the increase was not~~
424 ~~significant (reaching values of 124.62 µg kg⁻¹ fresh weight). The fact that the increase in~~
425 ~~galactinol is positively correlated with that of UDP-galactose seems to corroborate the~~
426 ~~synthesis of raffinose at this time (Table 3).~~ The concentration of UDP-galactose did not
427 significantly increase after CO₂ stress removal, reaching values of 124.62 µg kg⁻¹ fresh
428 weight in comparison with the 102.15 µg kg⁻¹ values reached in CO₂ stress (Table 3).
429 UDP-glucose content decreased in 40% CO₂ stressed fruit and it did not significantly
430 recover after transfer to air (517.75 and 524.39 µg kg⁻¹ fresh weight, respectively).
431 UDP-glucose can be converted to UDP-galactose and it is involved in several
432 biosynthetic pathways, including that involved in the synthesis of sucrose that reacts
433 with fructose-6-phosphate to make sucrose phosphate (Wind et al., 2010). CO₂ stress
434 modified the hexose to sucrose balance (Table 3) by decreasing the hexose to sucrose
435 ratio. This effect was reverted after CO₂ stress removal.

436

437 **Conclusions**

438 In this study, the trisaccharides 1-kestose, 6G-kestose and raffinose were characterized
439 and quantified in strawberries by HPLC-ESI-QTOF. While no 6-kestose was detected in
440 Mara des Bois strawberries, the other three trisaccharides were well-resolved on a
441 Hypercarb column, each with a clearly different and reproducible MS² spectrum. The
442 consumption of fermentative sugars under high CO₂ stress (3 d, 40 kPa CO₂) caused
443 marked osmotic depression that was associated with a decrease in the unfreezable water
444 to total water ratio, although this reverted after transfer to atmospheric CO₂

445 concentrations for 1 d. The removal from CO₂ stress promoted hexose accumulation by
446 triggering the use of sucrose to recover the 1-kestose and raffinose levels, with
447 galactinol a metabolite marker of this activated energy-conserving pathway. The
448 accumulation of both simple sugars, and of protective tri-FOS and raffinose, can assist
449 the osmotic adjustments and the re-establishment of water status after the imposition of
450 high CO₂ stress.

451

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455

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563

564 **Figure Captions**

- 565 Figure 1. (A) Total soluble solids (%). (B) Freezing onset temperature (°C). (C)
566 Unfreezable water (U_w) to total water (T_w) ratio in Mara des Bois strawberries at
567 harvest, after 3 d of storage at 0 °C in air (atmospheric CO₂) or when exposed to
568 40 kPa CO₂ (CO₂ stress), and after subsequent transfer to air for 1 d (CO₂ stress

569 removal). The error bars represent the standard deviation of the mean. Each letter
570 indicates significant differences in the means determined by the Tukey`s test ($P <$
571 0.05).

572 Figure 2. Ion chromatograms from HPLC-ESI-MS analysis corresponding to the 1-
573 kestose and 6G-kestose isomers, and to raffinose from lyophilized onion and
574 strawberry fruit, respectively. Collision energy = 30 eV.

575 Figure 3. Negative electrospray MS² scan spectra of trisaccharide isomers and raffinose
576 at a m/z of 503, collision energy = 30 eV: (A) 1-kestose; (B) 6G-kestose; and (C)
577 raffinose in strawberries.

578 Figure 4. Tri-FOS isomers: (A) 1-kestose, (B) 6G-kestose, (C) raffinose (mg kg⁻¹ fresh
579 weight), and (D) galactinol content (µg kg⁻¹ fresh weight) in Mara des Bois
580 strawberries at harvest, and after 3 d of storage at 0 °C in air (atmospheric CO₂) or
581 40 kPa CO₂ (CO₂ stress), and following their subsequent transfer to air for 1 d
582 (CO₂ stress removal). The error bars represent the standard deviation of the mean.
583 Each letter indicates significant differences between the means determined by the
584 Tukey`s test ($P < 0.05$).

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Figure 1

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Figure 2

Figure 3

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Figure 4

Table 1. Color parameters, pH, titratable acidity (TA) (malic acid (%) fresh weight), firmness (N) and water potential (ψ_w) in Mara des Bois strawberries at harvest, and after 3 d of storage at 0 °C in air (atmospheric CO₂) or 40 kPa CO₂ (CO₂ stress) and after transfer to air for 1 d (CO₂ stress removal).

	<i>L</i> *	<i>a</i> *	<i>C</i> *	pH	TA	Firmness	ψ_w
At harvest	28.74±2.6a	29.58±2.5c	29.86±2.6c	3.56±0.0a	0.73±0.0d	97.33±7.3a	-2.68±0.5a
Atmospheric CO ₂	34.23±2.6bc	23.79±2.3b	23.88±2.3b	3.80±0.0c	0.69±0.0b	111.29±9.4a	-1.94±0.7b
CO ₂ stress	33.32±2.6b	24.14±2.7b	24.19±2.7b	3.64±0.0b	0.67±0.0ab	179.66±20.7b	-2.15±0.3ab
CO ₂ stress removal	36.00±1.6c	20.97±1.4a	21.43±1.6a	3.66±0.0b	0.66±0.0a	183.16±0.6b	-2.04±0.3b

Data represent means ± SD of 3-5 samples per condition. Different letters in columns indicate significant differences between the means determined by the Tukey's test (P< 0.05).

Table 2. Characterization of tri-FOS, raffinose, galactinol, UDP-galactose and UDP-glucose compounds in *Fragaria vesca* Mara des Bois strawberries by Mass Spectrometry Detection in Negative Mode.

Peak	Rt (min) ^a	MS identification			MS ² identification				
		Exact Mass	Molecular ion [M-H]	Tentative Molecular Formula	Score (%)	MS ² (m/z) ^b	Standard	Column model	Tentative identification
1	7.2	503.1613		C ₁₈ H ₃₂ O ₁₆	97.82	323 , 179,	yes	Thermo Hypercarb column	1-kestose
2	8.65	503.1613		C ₁₈ H ₃₂ O ₁₆	98.31	323, 221, 179	*	Thermo Hypercarb column	6G-kestose
3	9.30	503.1637		C ₁₈ H ₃₂ O ₁₆	97.84	221 , 179, 323	yes	Thermo Hypercarb column	raffinose
<hr/>									
1	7.1	341.1089		C ₁₂ H ₂₂ O ₁₁	85.63	179 , 71	yes	Tracer Excel C8 120 ODS-B column	galactinol
2	10.43	565.0542		C ₁₅ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₁₇ P ₂	92.13	323	no	Tracer Excel C8 120 ODS-B column	UDP-galactose
3	10.91	565.0494		C ₁₅ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₁₇ P ₂	72.70	323	yes	Tracer Excel C8 120 ODS-B column	UDP-glucose

^aRt (min), retention time. ^bThe most abundant ions are shown in bold. These ions are isolated for fragmentation in negative mode. * (From lyophilized onion).

Table 3. UDP-galactose ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ fresh weight), UDP-glucose ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ fresh weight) and hexoses/sucrose ratio in Mara des Bois strawberries at harvest, and after 3 d of storage at 0 °C in air (atmospheric CO_2) or 40 kPa CO_2 (CO_2 stress) and transfer to air for 1 d (CO_2 stress removal).

	At harvest	Atmospheric CO_2	CO_2 stress	CO_2 Stress removal
UDP-galactose	130.19 \pm 18.1a	116.90 \pm 16.4	102.15 \pm 12.2a	124.62 \pm 22.9a
UDP-glucose	707.00 \pm 77.0b	573.19 \pm 52.6ab	517.75 \pm 48.8a	524.39 \pm 82.6a
Hexoses/sucrose	3.07 \pm 0.1c	2.65 \pm 0.1bc	1.91 \pm 0.1a	2.58 \pm 0.3b

Each value represents the mean \pm SD of the three biological replicates with two different technical measurements. Different letters in **columns** **rows** indicate significant differences between the means determined by the Tukey's test ($P < 0.05$).

Highlights

Osmotic depression caused by high CO₂ stress.

Involvement of 1-kestose and raffinose in water status recovery.

Galactinol as an early marker activated after CO₂ stress removal.

CO₂ treatment at 0 °C enhanced firmness of strawberry.